

An Analysis Of Execution Of Kisan Credit Card Scheme By Regional Rural Bank In Damoh District Of Madhya Pradesh

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Abstract

The KCC Scheme is the financial scheme in India and it is a non-discriminatory banking product in India. the replica of the KCC Scheme was prepared by NABARD on the guidance of the R.V. Gupta Committee on behalf of the Government of India. The main objectives of this study are to evaluate the execution of the KCC scheme in the term of No. of card issued and disbursed an amount of advance through the branches of Regional Rural Bank in Damoh district from the year 2015 to the year 2020, Present study is based on both types of data as primary data and secondary data also, the correlation research design has adopted for conducting this research. Finally, the present study concluded that the execution of the Kisan Credit scheme in the term of the total no. of cards issued and total no. of the disbursed amount of advance is not growing progressively during the period from the year 2015 to the year 2020 but both are highly correlated in each other.

Keywords:- Kisan Credit Card, Regional Rural Bank, Loan Amount, Scheme

Introduction:

The small marginal farmers have required the loan to perform the various agricultural operation as manuring, harvesting, seeding, and permanent improvement on land like digging the wells and tube wells, etc therefore farmers stretch their hands towards money lenders, they usually lend a small amount of loan at very high rates of interest to the farmers thus the repayment of the amount of loan is generally so difficult for the farmers, in order to get rids problem the Government of India had established the regional rural bank to provide financial facilities at concessional rate of interest to the farmers through implementing the financial schemes time to time, the Kisan Credit Scheme is one of the financial schemes among them, the KCC scheme was introduced in the year 1998-99 in India, the Model of KCC Scheme was prepared by NABARD (National Bank for Agricultural and Rural Development) under the guidance of the R.V. Gupta Committee on behalf of the Central Government of India.

The KCC scheme is beneficial to the small marginal farmer to provide advances on the concessional rate of interest to enhance the agriculture productivity of farmers through which they operate agricultural operations efficiently. The farmers are the beneficial persons who are availing with the KCC under this Scheme. The financial facilities are decided based on the scale of finance, the size of landholdings, cropping pattern and also depends on the judgment of banking officers.

The important aim of the KCC Scheme is to provide timely and adequate credit support to farmers from the formal banking system in a flexible, hassle-free, cost-effective manner, it plays an important role in the socio-economic development of farmers by providing on-demand financial assistance to them timely.

The Regional Rural Banks (RRBs) play an important role to fulfil the financial requirements of the poor, marginal farmers under the KCC scheme (Malaiya & Suryavanshi, 2021). From the year 1998-99, the KCC scheme has been implemented by public sector commercial banks, RRBs (Regional Rural Banks), and cooperative banks in the country. (Chhoidub & Pathania, 2017), the RRB is also offered credit facilities to the marginal poor, small, farmers of rural areas to fulfill their agricultural credit requirement timely by implementing the KCC scheme, KCC is the financial scheme that had been introduced to enhance the flow of credit to the rural sector because credit is one of the critical inputs in agriculture and effective means of development of farmers in India.

The Brief Profile of the KCC Scheme – A Study

The Kisan Credit Card Scheme centers around a revolving credit line facility and less stringent monitoring of actual use of loans, there are no collateral requirements for availing the financial loans under this scheme to the farmers because there is no requirement of the security deposit to qualify for the loan. The amount varies from bank to bank and also depends on the scale of finance—a formula based on the crop and size of landholding. The Kisan credit card Scheme plays an important role to provide agricultural loans for the development of farmers, the various financial institutions play a very important role in the implementation of the Kisan Credit Card Scheme by commercial banks, cooperative banks, regional rural banks, the Commercial banks are the largest lenders through regional rural banks and cooperative banks play an important role in many states of India. (Chanda, 2020). A KCC is allotted to a farmer who has registered under this scheme., the RRB is charged the 11-13% rate of interest on the repayment of the disbursed amount of loan if repayment of the disbursed amount of loan done by farmers within a year, then the 7% rate of interest on the disbursed amount of loan is charged by RRB however government provides the interest subvention up to 3% on the disbursed amount of loan to the farmer under this KCC scheme. The farmers or cultivators, joint cultivators, persons engaged in agricultural-based practices such as sowing, harvesting, etc are considered actual beneficiaries of the KCC scheme.

The Various Key Features of Kisan Credit Card Scheme

1. The Kisan credit card scheme is a widely accepted banking product.
2. Kisan credit card scheme offers the disbursed amount of loan at concessional rate of

interest to the farmers

3. The hassle-free credit facilitates by providing the Kisan credit card to its beneficiaries like farmers under the kisan credit card scheme,
4. The Kisan credit card provides flexible repayment options to the farmers.

The No. of Kisan Credit Cards issued in India

The number of cards issued was 7.84 lac in the year 1998-99 which increased to 129.82 lac in the year 2012-13 and registered a growth rate of 26.37 percent during the period from the year 1998-99 to the year 2012-13 in India (Kaur & Dhaliwal, 2018) The total no. of 6 regions such as east, west, north, south, central, north-east region have issued by RRB the no. of 2048000 cards in India, the Madhya Pradesh states belong to the central region, the RRB have issued second-largest total no. of 75000 cards in the year 2013 in Madhya Pradesh followed by the Uttar Pradesh in Central region, the total no. of largest 551000 cards issued in the year 2013 by RRB in Uttar Pradesh of Central region (Reserve Bank of India, 2013) The total no. of cards was 12253000, 12197000 issued by Regional Rural Bank in the year 2019, the year 2020 respectively in India, the total no. of 4 states as Uttar Pradesh, Uttarakhand, Madhya Pradesh, Chhattisgarh have issued the total no. of 4115000, 4031000 cards in the year 2019 and the year 2020 respectively by RRB in central region, the largest total no. of cards 4115000, 4031000 have issued by the RRB in the year 2019 and the year 2020 respectively in the central region among all the regions The Madhya Pradesh states belong to the central region, the RRB has issued second-largest total no. of 472000, 375000 cards in the year 2019 and the year 2020 respectively in Madhya Pradesh followed by the Uttar Pradesh because the total no. of largest 3436000, 3361000 cards issued in the year 2019 and the year 2020 respectively by RRB in Uttar Pradesh of Central region (Reserve Bank of India, 2020)

The Disbursed Amount of Loan under the KCC Scheme in India

the amount disbursed under the KCC scheme was Rs. 2310 crore in the year 1998-99 which increased to Rs. 126280 crores in the year 2012-13 and registered a growth rate of 22.72 percent during the period from the year 1998-99 to the year 2012-13 in India. The total no. of 6 regions such as east, west, north, south, central, north-east region has issued the no. of 2048000 cards by RRB in India, the total no. of 4 states as Uttar Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh, Uttarakhand, Chhattisgarh states have issued the largest amount of loan Rs. 48.1 billion by RRB in the Central Region, the RRB has issued second-largest total no. of the amount of loan Rs. 8 billion in Madhya Pradesh in the year 2013 followed by the Uttar Pradesh in Central Region, the total no. of the largest amount of loan Rs 30.6 billion disbursed by RRB in Uttar Pradesh of Central region in the year 2013 (Reserve Bank of India, 2013).

Reviews of Literature

Jainuddin, S. (2015). revealed in their study that the no. of 1133 lakhs of KCCs have been issued up to the end of 2011-12 by all the three agencies throughout the country and the overall cumulative amount disbursed was ₹ 13,55,332 crores, the total no. of the amount of Rs. 21,543.00 have disbursed against the total no. of 72.00 lakhs cards have issued by the RRB from the financial year 2006-2007 to the financial year 2011-2012 in Karnataka.

Sharma, C. P., & Singh, D. A. (2020). The total no. of the amount of Rs. 135149 crores have also disbursed against the total no. of KCC 238.66 lakhs have been issued the by the RRB during the period from the financial year 1998-99 to the year 2014-15 in India, the total no. of KCC 504079 have issued by the RRB in Madhya Pradesh as on 31 March 2015

Objectives of this Study

1. To study the Kisan credit card scheme.
2. To study the total no. of Kisan Credit Card have issued under the Kisan Credit Card Scheme during the year 2015 to the year 2020.
3. To evaluate the total amount of advance have disbursed under the Kisan Credit Card Scheme from the year 2015 to the year 2020
4. To provide the suggestions for implementation regarding the Kisan Credit Card Scheme

Research Methodology

The present study has been conducted in the Damoh district because such type of study has not been conducted in the Damoh district regarding the implementation of the KCC scheme through Regional Rural Banks' branches in Damoh district yet. The above objectives are determined on the basis of various literature reviews to conduct this study, the specific objectives are to evaluate the execution of the KCC scheme in the term of no. of card issued and disbursed an amount of advance through the branches of Regional Rural Bank in Damoh district from the year 2015 to the year 2020. This study belongs to the analytical, correlational research design adopted to evaluate the relationship between two variables as the total no. of KCC issued and total no. of the amount of disbursed advance by RRB to the beneficiaries of the KCC scheme. This study is based on secondary data and primary data, the secondary data have been collected from the Regional Office of Regional Rural Bank and the primary data have been collected by adopting the personal interview method, the interview has conducted from the 5 purposively selected banking officers of RRB of Damoh district. This period of this study belongs for 5 years, from 2015 to the year 2020.

The hypothesis of this Study

- H₀:** There is no significant relationship between the total no. of the disbursed amount of advance and total no. of cards issued under the KCC Scheme by RRB during the year 2015 to the year 2020
- H_a:** There is a significant relationship between the total no. of the disbursed amount of advance and the total no. of cards issued under the KCC Scheme by RRB during the year 2015 to 2020.

Implementation of Kisan Credit Card in Damoh District

The implementation of the Kisan Credit Card scheme depends on the total no. of cards have issued and the total no. of the amount of loans has disbursed by the overall branches of RRB from the year 2015 to the year 2020 in this study. The total no. of KCC 9386 have issued and the total no. of the amount of Rs. 658,16,0308 lakhs have also been disbursed by the overall

branches of RRB during the period: from 1 January 2015 to 31 December 2020 in Damoh district. For the better presentation of data regarding the implementation of the kisan credit scheme in Damoh district, the total no. of 3 tables have been listed below as table -1: No. of cards issued from the year 2015 to the year 2020, table -2 the disbursed amount of advance from the year 2015 to the year 2020, the table -3: the total no. of cards issued and the disbursed amount of advance respectively.

Table 1 No. of cards issued under the KCC scheme during the period: Years 2015 to 2020

BRANCH NAME	Year 2015	Year 2016	Year 2017	Year 2018	Year 2019	Year 2020
ABHANA	165	73	23	105	34	NA
BANAWAR	36	1	14	108	70	NA
BANDAKPUR	85	61	32	98	38	41
BANGAWN	79	33	82	126	29	8
BATIYAGARH	31	4	93	135	23	2
DAMOH	102	14	52	67	34	8
FATEHPUR	64	24	108	254	43	9
FUTERAKALA	NA	NA	3	6	NA	NA
GAISABAD	127	42	73	224	28	NA
HATTA	184	7	89	114	53	NA
HIRDAYPUR	NA	2	16	10	32	NA
JABERA	85	6	34	62	120	15
JHALON	NA	NA	6	19	33	NA
KALHARA KHEDA	NA	NA	2	3	9	NA
KILLAI NAKA DAMOH	2	102	NA	31	13	23
KISHUNGANJ	448	12	NA	119	49	6
KUMHARI	77	92	130	71	96	25
MADHIYADO	224	18	17	43	7	1
NARSINGGARH	45	49	77	32	12	106
NOHATA	14	49	64	106	59	27
PATERA	34	76	78	178	28	22
PATHARIYA	16	5	73	209	238	1
PURNA THANA DAMOH	NA	NA	9	5	13	NA
RANEH	79	67	84	201	NA	2
SINGRAMPUR	57	14	88	48	36	3
TARADEHI	354	2	83	199	117	NA
TEJGARH	25	81	57	92	25	3
TENDUKHEDA	38	23	54	100	29	12
TOTAL	2371	857	1441	2765	1268	314

Source: Regional office of Regional Rural Bank, Beside Red Rose Hotel, Damoh. Dated on 03/06/2021

Table 1 reveals the no. of Kisan Credit Cards have issued during the period: from the year 2015 to the year 2020 under the KCC scheme by the overall branches of Regional Rural Bank in Damoh district, the total no. of cards 2371, 857, 1441, 2765, 1268, 314 have been issued in the years 2015, 2016, 2017, 2018, 2019, 2020 respectively. One can also evaluate from table 1 that the total no. of the maximum of 2765 cards have been issued by the overall bank branches of RRBs of Damoh district in the year 2018. The total no. of minimum cards 314 have issued in the year 2020.

Causes of the Non-Progressive Growth: No. of Cards Issued by RRB

On November 8, 2016 currency notes of denomination of 500 Rs and 1000 Rs were demonetised (SBN[♦]), the circulation of currency had highly affected during the time of demonetisation period (Impact of Demonetisation on the Financial Sector, 2017) in this regards the application for availing the Kisan credit card towards applicants like farmers (beneficiaries of KCC Scheme) had received by the RRBs' officer comparatively low in the year 2016 and the year 2017 rather than in the year 2015 and they had not interested to join KCC Scheme because they would like to grab the newly printed currencies in exchange of demonetised currencies (old currencies) in the year 2016 and the year 2017 (Rajput & Patel, 2021). During the election period, the government provides the incentives of waiving loans to farmers (Malaiya & Suryavanshi, 2021) and they are highly encouraged and motivated towards financial schemes to avail with financial facilities that have been provided by the financial institutions like banks (RRB, SBI) (Khare & Meshram, 2021) thus in the year 2018, the total no. of maximum cards 2765 have issued by the RRBs in Damoh districts. The KCC Scheme is widely accepted, the total no. of almost 89 - 92% of households of farmers has aware and availed with this Scheme (Meshram, 2021).

Table 2 The disbursed amount of Advance during the Years: 2015 to 2020

BRANCH NAME	Year 2015	Year 2016	Year 2017	Year 2018	Year 2019	Year 2020
ABHANA	6683400	5882900	1473400	6440718	1217500	NA
BANAWAR	1632200	7800	743000	8079200	2859100	NA
BANDAKPUR	5240900	4122000	1776075	6637600	1935400	3405400
BANGAWN	4746700	1400200	6448100	10155832	1986504	666000
BATIYAGARH	1819800	696100	5561400	12680690	1702700	104100
DAMOH	6691100	662400	3092806	5034259	2292592	472400
FATEHPUR	2686350	1328500	5514191	18390500	1868200	594000
FUTERAKALA	NA	NA	253000	378000	NA	NA
GAISABAD	6994700	3623700	6538975	21708472	1162805	NA

[♦] SBNs (Specified bank notes) : denomination of 500 Rs and 1000 Rs.

HATTA	12689800	767000	8479080	11445460	3389795	NA
HIRDAYPUR	NA	230700	1561000	515500	1368000	NA
JABERA	4574600	824500	2780000	4844860	6695300	1351000
JHALON	NA	NA	240000	620000	915000	NA
KALHARA						
KHEDA	NA	NA	109000	175000	760000	NA
KILLAI NAKA						
DAMOH	190200	4566100	NA	1276700	558974	1384800
KISHUNGANJ	20152500	675000	NA	9298100	3876100	811000
KUMHARI	4738700	6213800	7147100	5450450	5709701	1305700
MADHIYADO	9290900	1242000	781500	2191400	220000	77000
NARSINGHGARH	3082500	2883900	5462900	2186756	365000	7003450
NOHATA	1116400	3539700	5298400	11612900	2385800	1145700
PATERA	3294000	8747140	7109000	16652040	2120400	1556700
PATHARIYA	960000	332000	6829500	21298100	17664670	76000
PURNA THANA						
DAMOH	NA	NA	412700	1579000	400000	NA
RANEH	7946000	7278500	8161000	21261600	NA	63000
SINGRAMPUR	2231500	821800	8209200	3483500	3086300	331000
TARADEHI	19062700	110000	6028350	15120730	9337800	NA
TEJGARH	1480800	5011720	4424160	6833460	1288940	149600
TENDUKHEDA	2448900	1439215	4181988	7660800	1946700	1042400
TOTAL	129754650	62406675	108615825	233011627	77113281	21539250

Source: Regional office of Regional Rural Bank, Beside Red Rose Hotel, Damoh. Dated on 03/06/2021

Table 2 reveals the no. of the amount of advance that has disbursed under the KCC scheme during the year 2015 to the year 2020 by the overall branches of Regional Rural Bank that the total no. of the maximum amount of advance of Rs 233011627 has been disbursed by the overall bank branches of RRBs of Damoh district in the year 2018 but the total no. of the minimum amount of advance of Rs. 19754650 have disbursed in the year 2015 by the overall branches of RRB of Damoh district. The disbursing amount of loan depends on the total no. of cards issued, if the total no. of cards issued is more then the disbursed amount of loan is also more, if the total no. of cards issued is low then the disbursed amount of loan is also low from current year to subsequent year (Soni, 2021).

Table 3 Total no. of cards issued and disbursed an amount of advance

Year	Total no. of Card issued under the KCC Scheme	Total no. of the amount of advance disbursed Under the KCC Scheme
2015	2371	129754650
2016	857	62406675
2017	1441	108615825
2018	2765	233011627
2019	1268	77113281
2020	314	21539250

Source: Based on table no. 1 and table no. 2

Table 3 reveal the total no. of cards issued and the amount advance have disbursed under the KCC scheme by the overall 28 branches from the year 2015 to the year 2020, the total no. of the amount of advance 129754650, 62406675, 108615825, 233011627, 77113281, 2153950 has disbursed against the total no. of cards 2371, 857, 1441, 2765, 1268, 314 have issued respectively by RRB from the year 2015 to the year 2020. The total no. of the maximum amount of advance of Rs 233011627 has been disbursed and the total no. of maximum Cards 2765 have issued in the year 2018 (Refer [table 1](#) and [table 2](#)).

Hypothesis Testing: -

H₀: There is no significant relationship between the total disbursed amount of advance and the total no. of cards issued under the KCC Scheme by RRB during the year 2015 to the year 2020.

H_a: There is a significant relationship between the total disbursed amount of advance and the total no. of cards issued under the KCC Scheme by RRB during the year 2015 to 2020

Table 4 Karl Pearson Correlation Test

Variables	Particular	Total no. of card issued	Total no. of the amount of disbursed advance
Total no. of card issued	Pearson Correlation	1	.942**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.005
	N	6	6
Total no. of the disbursed amount of advance	Pearson Correlation	.942**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.005	
	N	6	6
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).			

Source: SPSS Data Analysis Software (based on [table 3](#) and [fig. 1](#))

Table 4 reveal about the Karl Pearson Correlation test belonging to the Bivariate Correlation indicates the correlation between two variables such as total no. of card issued and total no. of the amount of advance disbursed under the KCC Scheme. The Karl Pearson correlation test: 0.942 ($.005 < .05$), ($.005 < 0.01$) indicate about the correlation between the variables, ($.005 < .05$), ($.005 < 0.01$) indicate about the significant correlation between the variables, R-value = 0.942 indicate the relationship between the variables. Hence, our null hypothesis is rejected and we fail to reject the alternative hypothesis of this study hereby we can say that there is a significant relationship between the total disbursed amount of advance and the total no. of cards issued under the KCC Scheme by RRB during the year 2015 to 2020,

One can evaluate from [table 3](#) and [table 4](#) that in the year 2015, the total no. of 2371 cards issued in respect of the total no. of the amount of advance of Rs. 129754650 have disbursed under the KCC Scheme by the overall branches of the RRB but in the year 2016, the total no. of 857 cards issued in respects of the total no. of the amount of advance of Rs. 62406675 have disbursed under the KCC scheme by the overall branches of the RRB, we observed the relationship between the total no. of cards issued and the total no. of the disbursed amount of advance then we evaluate that the total no. of card issued had reduced by 1514 (2371 - 857) from the year 2015 to the year 2016 and the total no. of the disbursed amount of advance had reduced by Rs. 67347975 (Rs. 129754650 – Rs. 62406675) from the year 2015 to the year 2016, the similar relationship between the total no. of cards issued and the total no. of the disbursed amount of advance then we also evaluate that the total no. of cards issued have enhanced by the no. of 584, 1324 cards from the year 2016 to the year 2017, from the year 2017 to the year 2018 respectively and the total no. of the disbursed amount of advance had also enhanced by Rs. 46209150 (108615825-62406675) and Rs. 124395802 (Rs.233011627-108615825) from the year 2016 to the year 2017, from the year 2017 to the year 2018 respectively, one can also reveal with the similar types of relationship again between the total no. of cards issued and the total no. of the disbursed amount of advance then we also found again that the total no. of cards issued had reduced again by 1497 (2765 -1268) and enhanced by 954 (1268-314) from the year 2018 to the year 2019 and from the year 2019 to the year 2020 respectively, the total no. of disbursed amount of advance had also reduced by Rs. 155898346 (Rs. 233011627 – Rs. 77113281) and also enhanced by Rs.55574031 (21539250-77113281) from the year 2018 to the year 2019, 2019 to the year 2020 respectively, one can easily be evaluated that the no. of issued cards have enhanced or reduced from the year to next consecutive year then the disbursed amount of advance is also enhanced or reduced from the year to next consecutive year so we can say that there is a significant relationship between the status of total disbursed amount of advance and the status of total no. of card issued by RRB during the year 2015 to 2020 (Refer [table 4](#)).

In the year 2018, the total no. of the maximum of 2371 cards have issued then the total no. of the maximum amount of Rs. 129754650 have disbursed under the KCC Scheme by the branches of RRB, while branches of RRB issued the total no. of maximum Kisan Credit Card then the branches of RRB disbursed the total no. of the maximum amount of advances to the farmers.

In the year 2020, the total no. of the lowest 314 cards have been issued then the total no. of the lowest amount of Rs. 21539250 have disbursed under the KCC Scheme by the branches of

RRB, one can say that while branches of RRB issued the total no. of minimum Kisan Credit Card then the branches of RRB disbursed the total no. of the minimum amount of advances to the farmers.

Conclusions

1. The Kisan Credit Card Scheme is one of the innovative, widely accepted, highly appreciated, and non-discriminatory banking product in India. The execution of the Kisan Credit scheme in the term of the total no. of cards issued and total no. of the disbursed amount of advance is not growing progressively during the period from the year 2015 to the year 2020 but both are highly correlated in each other because while the total no. of kisan credit cards have issued more then the total no. of the amount of advance has also disbursed more otherwise total no. of kisan credit cards have issued low then the total no. of the amount of advance have also disbursed low under the KCC scheme by the RRB.
2. The implementation of the KCC Scheme is highly affected by the political and economic environment, the no. of the farmers were being highly interested the no of farmers were not being interested to join or avail with KCC scheme during the demonetisation period but during the election period loan waives policy of government plays an important role to attract them towards the KCC Scheme, they are highly interested to join or availed with KCC scheme. and The KCC scheme is widely accepted, the total no. of almost 89 - 92% of households of farmers has aware and availed with this Scheme (Meshram, 2021).
3. The largest total no. of cards 4115000, 4031000 have issued by the RRB in the year 2019 and the year 2020 respectively in the central region among all the regions, the second-largest total no. of cards 467000, 470000 have issued by RRB in the year 2019 and the year 2020 respectively in Madhya Pradesh state belongs to the central region (Reserve Bank of India, 2020).

Suggestions

1. The RRB should issue the no. of Kisan Credit Card comparatively more from the current year to subsequent year from which the total no. of the disbursed amount of advance would also comparatively more from the current year to subsequent year because both are highly correlated with each other then they achieved the progressive growth in the term of the no. of card issued and total no. of the disbursed amount of advance.
2. RRB should be extended the prescribed limit of the disbursed amount of loan from Rs. 30000 – Rs.34000 to Rs. 50000 – Rs. 54000 through determining the scale of finance for certain crops such as soybean, wheat, gram.
3. The RBI should advise the RRB for determining the separate crop-wise scale of finance to calculate the disbursed amount of loan through DLTC (District Level Technical Committee) based on per acre rather than per hectare basis for the socio-economic development of Small and Poor farmers and the government should extend

the subvention rate of interest from 3% to 5% for the small farmers on the repayment of the amount of loan timely through which implementation of KCC Scheme would be a highly impressive and attractive scheme to the farmers.

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